

ISSUES OF ORGANIZING THE RISK MANAGEMENT MECHANISM IN ENSURING THE FINANCIAL STABILITY OF INSURANCE COMPANIES

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Abstract. In this scientific thesis, the possibilities of ensuring financial stability in insurance companies through the effective organization of the financial risk management mechanism are scientifically based. In the following years, the priorities of the reform of the insurance system in the Republic of Uzbekistan and the scientific conclusions on the organization of risk management in insurance companies were presented.

Keywords: financial risk, risk management, strategy, KPI, underwriter, insurance, investment, financial stability, insurance obligations.

In the development of the financial market in Uzbekistan, the systematic analysis of the insurance market, which is one of its main segments, and the effective use of foreign best practices in ensuring the financial stability of insurance companies is of great importance. We should note that in recent years, they have carried effective workout on the comprehensive development of the insurance market in our country. Adoption of the Decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated August 2, 2019 No. PQ-4412 "On measures to reform the insurance market of the Republic of Uzbekistan and ensure its rapid development",

insurance companies created the ground for the implementation of fundamental reforms in terms of innovative development of activities¹.

Today, the organization and effective implementation of risk management is a priority task for companies operating in various directions. Companies can cover several risks in the organization of large-scale risk management. We should note that the company reflects the relevant risk management directions in its activities based on the nature of its activity.

We understood risk management in insurance activity as an activity aimed at assessing and quantifying the probability and financial impact of events that may occur to clients by the insurance company, and distributing the risks of these events among other insurance companies in the market. Risk management work typically involves mathematical and statistical modeling to determine the appropriate premium coverage and value of insurance risk. In order to achieve the strategic goals of enterprises, it is necessary to take into account the above in order to create the right risk strategy and ensure adequate risk management (Table 1).

An insurance company should pay attention to the following when managing risks in its activities:

- assessment of market strategy and reinsurance procedures to adapt the company to risks and optimize the company's goals;
- properly explain the risks and changes in demand rates to clients in order to move to a more market-oriented, risk-based pricing method that ensures efficient deployment of capital and reduction of losses in various situations;
- taking into account existing requirements to increase the efficiency and profitability of these processes.

¹ O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining 2019 yil 2 avgustdagi PQ-4412-sonli “O‘zbekiston Respublikasining sug‘urta bozorini isloh qilish va uning jadal rivojlanishini ta’minlash chora-tadbirlari to‘g‘risida”gi Qarori.

Insurance strategy assessment, design and implementation
Assessment, design, implementation of the basics of insurance risk
Evaluating, designing and implementing insurance risk portfolios and valuation methodology
Assessment, design and implementation of insurance risk statements
KPI design of the requirements function
Introduction of product sector strategy
Pricing of insurance products
KPI design of the underwriting function
Designing a reinsurance program

Table 1. Aspects that should be taken into account when creating a risk strategy in insurance companies ²

The main goal of any risk management is to anticipate future risks and prevent or at least minimize possible losses. Risk management is one of the main functions of insurance companies because, unlike many other industries, insurance companies deal with risk assessment and coverage. In order to adapt to an increasingly complex business environment, insurance companies are developing internal risk management, including more advanced data analytics tools and technologies to better support underwriting, pricing and claims management, and investment risk prevention. it is necessary to start their practice.

² Created by the author

Today's risks in the activities of insurance companies arise as a result of inconsistent internal processes or processes caused by some uncontrollable external factors. Risks of insurance companies are characterized by probabilities of occurrence.

Traditional risk management among insurance companies focuses on:

1. Underwriting risks;
2. Adequacy of reserves and reinsurance of insurance companies to cover potential losses;
3. Risk management in the investment portfolio of insurance companies.

The statistical model of risk management is based on the operation of insurance companies in uncertain conditions. Before making management decisions, risk management departments of insurance companies need to pre-analyze various types of risks using a probabilistic approach. This approach makes it possible to identify risks and take measures aimed at minimizing the occurrence of negative consequences for companies. An additional advantage of the model is that this model takes into account the real activity of the company. Here, each risk can be implemented in different combinations with different levels of probability. This can have negative consequences for one company and advantages for another.

In the world insurance market, insurers provide more than 1,000 types of insurance services, 300 of which are aimed at life insurance, taking into account the needs and wishes of policyholders. In our country, many types of insurance, for example, the obligations of financial institutions, the obligations of directors and managers of executive bodies to shareholders are not insured, one of the urgent tasks is to ensure financial stability by increasing the types of insurance. According to the analysis, there are a number of problems in this field that are specific not only to our republic, but also to some countries. This is mainly due to the lack of effective communication between insurance companies and the population, and the low efficiency of service due to the delay in responding to customer requests. In addition, the fact that the main share of insurance premiums - about 66% - corresponds to the

city of Tashkent and the Tashkent region is the basis for saying that the high geographical location of the insurance market is also one of the existing problems.

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